

ON THE MOLAR ZERO FLUIDITY VOLUMES OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS.

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Newton Friend has shown that the quantity V_0 , the molar volume at zero fluidity is an additive function of atoms and linkages in a large number of compounds. He has calculated the atomic and structural constants for some atoms and linkages. The present work is an extension of the above to nitrogen, chlorine, bromine, iodine and the co-ordinate link with an increase in co-valency (associated hydroxylic compounds). The atomic or linkage constants found for these are 6.0, 18.0, 23.0, 29.0 and 6.6 respectively.

Newton Friend (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **34**, 813) derived the relationship $\phi = k(v_0^{\frac{8}{3}} - v_0^{\frac{8}{3}})$ between fluidity (ϕ) and specific volume (v) of a liquid, v_0 denoting the extrapolated specific volume of the supercooled liquid at the extrapolated temperature of zero fluidity or infinite viscosity. This is based on the assumption that the molecules are spherical and that the attractive force between the molecules varies inversely as the eighth power of the distance between their centres. The quantity Mv_0 or V_0 (M =molecular weight), termed the molar zero fluidity volume, was shown to be an additive function of atoms and linkages in the molecule, and some atomic and structural constants were evaluated (*loc. cit.*).

The present work is an extension of the above to nitrogen and halogen compounds, simple co-ordinate linkages and to co-ordinate linkages accompanied by an increase in co-valency of hydrogen from one to two as in the case of associated hydroxylic compounds. By analysing the viscosity and density data available, values of V_0 were arrived at (given in Table I) and the following atomic constants evaluated :—

N, 6.0; Cl, 18.0; Br, 23.0; I, 29.0.

A simple co-ordinate linkage has the same value as the ordinary double bond, as would appear from the values for nitrobenzene and the nitrotoluenes.

Figure 1 shows the extent of validity of the equation, $\phi = k(v_0^{\frac{8}{3}} - v_0^{\frac{8}{3}})$. Lines 1 to 6 exhibit the kind of discrepancy ($\phi_{\text{obs.}} - \phi_{\text{calc.}}$) found in most

substance. Generally the discrepancies are very small. In case of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-phenitidine, *o*-bromoaniline and *m*-toluidine, the discrepancies are greater, *o*- and *m*-phenitidine (lines 8 and 7 in the figure) showing the largest discrepancies. In case of *o*-phenitidine (line 8) the discrepancy goes up to almost 100 per cent at the lowest temperature. But, it has to be borne in mind that the value of ϕ itself is very small at this temperature and consequently a small experimental error would be enormously magnified when calculated in the form of percentage error. Even if the compounds showing large discrepancies are left out of account, there is no appreciable change in the calculated atomic constants.

FIG. 1.

Line 1 refers to *o*-bromotoluene" 3 " tri-*n*-butylamine

" 5 " methyl alcohol

" 7 " *m*-phenitidineLine 2 refers to *m*-bromoaniline" 4 " *o*-chlorotoluene

" 6 " ethyl iodide

" 8 " *o*-phenitidine

TABLE I.

Substance	Mol. formula	<i>k</i> .	$V_0(\text{obs.})^*$	$V_0(\text{calc.})^{**}$	% Diff.
Nitrobenzene	$C_6H_5NO_2$	672.7	97.5	97.9	+0.4
Aniline	C_6H_7N	446.5	89.0	88.1	-1.0
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	C_7H_9N	507.8	105.0	105.1	0.0
<i>o</i> -Nitrotoluene	$C_7H_7O_2N$	638.0	113.3	114.9	+1.3
<i>m</i> -Nitrotoluene	$C_7H_7O_2N$	698.0	114.4	114.9	+0.4
<i>o</i> -Phenitidine	$C_8H_{11}ON$	382.3	127.9	130.1	+1.7
<i>m</i> -Phenitidine	$C_8H_{11}ON$	400.0	129.3	130.1	+0.6
<i>p</i> -Phenitidine	$C_8H_{11}ON$	375.0	129.1	130.1	+0.7
<i>n</i> -Triamylamine	$C_{15}H_{33}N$	229.7	277.0	273.3	-1.3
<i>iso</i> Triamylamine	$C_{15}H_{33}N$	242.0	279.9	273.3	-2.4
Tri- <i>n</i> -butylamine	$C_{12}H_{27}N$	313.0	227.7	222.3	-2.4
Diethyl ammonium picrate	$C_{10}H_{14}O_7N_4$	305.9	228.8	232.0	+1.4
Di- <i>n</i> -butyl ammonium picrate	$C_{14}H_{22}O_7N_4$	163.3	301.8	300.0	-0.6
Tri- <i>n</i> -butyl ammonium picrate	$C_{18}H_{30}O_7N_4$	278.6	367.9	368.0	0.0
Tetra- <i>n</i> -butyl ammonium picrate	$C_{22}H_{38}O_7N_4$	133.3	424.0	436.0	+2.7
<i>n</i> -Cetyl ammonium picrate	$C_{22}H_{38}O_7N_4$	41.7	444.1	436.0	-1.8
Di- <i>n</i> -cetyl ammonium picrate	$C_{38}H_{76}O_7N_4$	58.8	728.0	708.0	-2.8
<i>o</i> -Chlorotoluene	C_7H_7Cl	732.9	109.0	108.9	-0.1
<i>m</i> -Chlorotoluene	C_7H_7Cl	711.1	109.2	108.9	-0.2
<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene	C_7H_7Cl	720.0	109.5	108.9	-0.5
Ethyl bromide	C_2H_5Br	2242.6	62.8	61.1	-2.7
<i>o</i> -Bromotoluene	C_7H_7Br	1206.5	116.5	113.3	-2.8
<i>m</i> -Bromotoluene	C_7H_7Br	1246.6	110.1	113.3	+2.8
<i>p</i> -Bromotoluene	C_7H_7Br	1246.6	110.1	113.3	+2.8
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	C_6H_6NBr	1253.8	107.4	106.2	-1.1
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline	C_6H_6NBr	1175.4	107.2	106.2	-0.9
Methyl iodide	CH_3I	4214.3	49.5	50.2	+1.4
Ethyl iodide	C_2H_5I	2711.1	68.6	67.2	-2.0
<i>n</i> Propyl iodide	C_3H_7I	2000.0	85.5	84.2	-1.5
<i>iso</i> Propyl iodide	C_3H_7I	1929.8	86.7	84.2	-3.0

* Obtained from density and viscosity data.

** Calculated with the constants derived by Newton Friend and by the author.

The agreement is fairly good except in a few cases where the difference rises up to nearly 3%.

It appeared worth while to examine the case of a few associated liquids (co-ordination with increase in co-valency). Data on viscosity and density could be obtained for methyl alcohol (0-60°), ethyl alcohol (0-70°), *n*-propyl alcohol (0-90°) and acetic acid (20-110°). Throughout the temperature ranges shown against them, the plot of ϕ against $v^{\frac{8}{3}}$ gave a straight line for each of the liquids. This indicates the constancy of their degree of association over these ranges, as is well known from other considerations (Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **12**, 913). $V_{0(\text{obs.})}$ and $V_{0(\text{calc.})}$ for these liquids, as obtained from their normal molecular weights (corresponding to ordinary chemical formulae) are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Substance	Mol. formula	k .	$V_{0(\text{obs.})}$	$V_{0(\text{calc.})}$	% Diff.
Methyl alcohol	CH ₄ O	476.0	37.4	33.2	-12.6
Ethyl alcohol	C ₂ H ₆ O	300.0	54.9	50.2	-9.4
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	C ₃ H ₈ O	264.7	71.7	67.2	-6.3
Acetic acid	C ₂ H ₄ O ₂	566.0	53.5	51.0	-5.0

It is seen that there is a large percentage difference in every case, the calculated values being always much lower than the observed values. Taking into account the actual molecular weights of the liquids as obtained from their degrees of association over these temperature ranges (calculated by the Eötvös-Ramsay method; Prasad, (*loc. cit.*), new values for V_0 could be obtained. The next problem was to see if a constant corresponding to a co-ordinate linkage with simultaneous increase in the co-valency of hydrogen existed. The method applied to test this is illustrated in the case of methyl alcohol. Methyl alcohol (CH₄O) is 3.6 or nearly 4 times associated. The molecular weight is 4×32 or 128. Four molecules are held by three co-ordinate linkages involving an increase in the co-valency of hydrogen, thus—

The molecular formula can be written as (CH₄O)₄ or C₄H₁₆O₄. $V_{0(\text{obs.})}$ corresponding to C₄H₁₆O₄ is obtained by multiplying v_0 by the molecular weight corresponding to C₄H₁₆O₄. Subtracting from $V_{0(\text{obs.})}$ the sum of

the atomic constants corresponding to the above formula, we get the value for three such co-ordinate linkages to be 16.8. Hence, the value of the constant corresponding to one such co-ordinate link is 5.6. The same method is applied for finding out the constant for a co-ordinate link with simultaneous increase in co-valency of hydrogen in the cases of ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol and acetic acid. The mean value of the constant is found to be 6.6. The difference in the values for a co-ordinate linkage with and without increase in co-valency has its parallel in the parachor and there is nothing unexpected about it.

Table III shows the difference between the observed and calculated values of V_0 for the associated compounds. The calculations have been made on the basis that association, as determined by the Eötvos-Ramsay method is correct and that the constant corresponding to a co-ordinate linkage with simultaneous increase in co-valency of hydrogen is 6.6.

TABLE III.

Substance	Mol. formula	Degree of association	$V_0(\text{obs.})$	$V_0(\text{calc.})$	% Diff.
Methyl alcohol	CH_4O	3.6 (4 approx.)	149.6	152.6	+2.0
Ethyl alcohol	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$	3	164.7	163.8	-0.6
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	$\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}$	2.1 (2 approx.)	143.4	141.0	-1.7
Acetic acid	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$	2	107.0	108.6	+1.5

The data were taken from the Tables Annuelles, Vol. XI (1931-34), Landolt Börnstein Tabellen and the International Critical Tables.

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